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Author for correspondence:
e-mail: rj.bhl@cbs.dk

Craft and the ethics of consolation: slow organizing in the Anthropocene

Rasmus Johnsen and Marta Gasparin

Department of Business Humanities and Law, Copenhagen Business School, Frederiksberg, Denmark

RJ, 0000-0003-1649-612X; MG, 0000-0001-6934-2525

This article develops the concept of slow organizing to explore how communities can respond to irreversible ecological loss in the Anthropocene. Drawing on ethnographic research with textile artist Birgitta Nordström, who weaves shrouds for stillborn children, we examine how time-sensitive, materially embedded and emotionally attuned practices can facilitate collective mourning. Rather than treating grief as a private or individual pathology, we argue that slow organizing turns mourning into a shared, generative and practical labour. By attending to the embodied, relational and anticipatory dimensions of this work, the article demonstrates how slow organizing can cultivate forms of care and responsibility that sustain communities facing ongoing planetary change.

This article is part of the theme issue 'The biosphere in the Anthropocene'.

1. Introduction: a new kind of sorrow

Framed as a geological marker, the Anthropocene usually takes shape through climate data, scientific models and policy debates. Together, these accumulate as proof of humanity's negative impacts on the planet. The emotional response this data elicits is evident in environmentalists' rhetoric, which often expresses 'frenetic, desperate activism': the conviction that immediate action is imperative because 'the earth is going to disappear [and] the planet as we know it is going to be gone—we've got to do something' [1, p. xi]. If, as the data suggest, we are now entering the 'climate endgame' [2], then only two emotional responses seem viable: defiance or resignation. Either we cling to the fragile hope that catastrophe can still be averted and act accordingly, or we abandon hope altogether.

However, in parallel, a different framing of the Anthropocene has begun to emerge in public discourse—one that engages more directly with the question of how to *feel* about climate change. This framing is, admittedly, messier and more ambiguous, yet it traces the contours of a new emotional landscape—one that may open a broader spectrum of ways to move forward in the face of planetary change.

At the heart of this shift is what Pettman and Thacker [3, p. xi] call a 'new kind of sorrow'. This feeling is captured in a range of emerging concepts, each emphasizing different facets of emotional response. For example, environmental melancholia, as described by Lertzman [4], refers to a persistent and unresolved mourning for ecological loss, while environmental grief [5] and ecological grief [1,6] highlight the acute bereavement experienced as ecosystems degrade and disappear. Other terms foreground related but distinct dimensions: ecodistress, as discussed by Marks and Hickman [7], encompasses broader feelings of anxiety, helplessness and moral distress linked to environmental change. Solastalgia [8] captures the distress produced by the transformation of familiar places while one still inhabits them.

These emotional responses arise in the space between two poles: on one side, the often-misguided debate over whether climate science is 'settled'

enough to justify long-term decisions; on the other, the lived reality of escalating wildfires, vanishing ecosystems and irreversible transformations across the planet. Together, they mark an emerging affective landscape that complicates conventional narratives of hope and catastrophe. Here, a series of pressing existential questions arise: What futures can be imagined when the foundations of the biosphere are unravelling? What forms of care might be extended to something disappearing so gradually its absence becomes nearly invisible? How should we mourn the death of a species, a place or a way of life? In the end, who—or what—will remain to grieve the vanishing of humanity? And is the planet even ‘ours’ to grieve in the first place?

What first stands out in this emerging framing of the Anthropocene is its recognition that climate change is not merely a problem to solve or a crisis to overcome, but a condition we must learn to live with and through—an unfolding reality for which we have no final script or shared language. It is not an isolated event to be managed and contained, but a chronic condition that reshapes our emotional, social and ecological existence. Grief and mourning are not responses external to this condition—they are constitutive of it. They reflect a growing awareness of irreversible loss, and the fundamental human need to seek connection, care and meaning in the face of what can no longer be undone.

At the same time, this framing gestures towards something deeper: a meditation on the human capacity to render the unbearable bearable. Mourning becomes not only an acknowledgement of loss but also a form of resilience—a way of orienting ourselves to a future that neither clings to false hope nor succumbs to despair. If we are, as Pettman and Thacker suggest, witnessing a ‘rift between the planet and its now temporary human inhabitants’ [3, p. xi], then this rift must be navigated not solely through technical solutions, but through collective acts of endurance. This opens space for new forms of care to emerge amid planetary change.

In this sense, the capacity to mourn together—to share the weight of grief and to find solace in the act of bearing witness—is not the end of grief, but the beginning of something else. It marks the transformation of grief into a generative force, one entangled with hope. As Lesley Head [9] reminds us, hope is not the absence of difficult emotions, but their companion. It arises through practice and through building the conditions in which we can live on with what has been lost. Yet if mourning in the Anthropocene demands new forms of collective practice, it also requires us to reconsider how we organize it. In this article, we propose *slow organizing* as one such mode: a way of structuring collective life that resists urgency and instrumentalization, instead attending to the temporal, material and emotional work of shared mourning. By foregrounding practices that are time-sensitive, materially embedded and relationally attuned, slow organizing offers a way to hold grief communally, creating space for consolation without closure.

This understanding will guide the trajectory of the essay. We begin by examining the discourse on mourning in the Anthropocene. This discussion underscores how the challenge lies not only in acknowledging personal experiences of grief, but in transforming them into collective practices of mourning. Framing mourning as a political and social achievement allows it to function both as a form of resistance and as a generative mode of organizing, especially when viewed through the tension between urgency and slowness.

From there, we turn to a concrete example: the weaving practice of Birgitta Nordström. Her work—creating shrouds for stillborn children—embodies an ethics of consolation rooted in the slow organizing of shared space for grief. Through this practice, Nordström invites reflection on how to live with loss, rather than overcome it, which will become central in learning how to live in the Anthropocene and through climate change. Finally, drawing on this case, we reflect on what it means to organize in and through mourning. We argue that slow practices offer a form of resilience—one not based in the promise of resolution or progress, but in the ability to endure, adapt and care together amid the uncertainties of a damaged planet.

2. Grief and mourning in the Anthropocene

In 1947, a monument was built in Wyalusing State Park, Wisconsin. Given the timing, one might assume it commemorated human suffering or war. But this monument was not for people—it was for a bird. The Wisconsin Society for Ornithology erected it in memory of the passenger pigeon, a once-abundant species that vanished in 1914. At the dedication, conservationist Aldo Leopold delivered a speech, later captured in his essay ‘On a Monument to the Pigeon’. He reflected on our ancestors, who hunted mammoths without hesitation, on the sportsman who shot the last wild pigeon and on the sailor who clubbed the final dodo—men who barely thought of what they had done. Yet now, Leopold observed, we mourn what they did not. And in that mourning, he argued, lies the truest proof of human superiority—not in our intelligence or ambition, but in our capacity to mourn what we have lost [10, p. 18f.].

Leopold’s perspective on mourning is intriguing for several reasons. Grief and mourning are frequently treated as synonymous, typically seen as innate human responses to loss. Grief motivates mourning, and mourning provides a means to express grief. Psychoanalytic theories, for instance, emphasize grief as a natural emotional reaction to loss and highlight the importance of processing it in healthy ways, contrasting this with pathological failures to mourn [1].¹ By characterizing mourning as a uniquely human achievement, Leopold implicitly distinguishes mourning from grief, emphasizing mourning as rooted specifically in human culture and social interactions. Mourning, in this sense, is not merely personal sorrow but a socially oriented practice involving the collective sharing and acknowledgement of loss [11]. For Leopold, this distinctly human capacity goes beyond individual pain, highlighting mourning as a communal process grounded in cultural interactions that cannot be taken for granted.

¹There is a rich psychoanalytic tradition of conceptualizing mourning, notably beginning with Freud’s distinction between mourning and melancholia, and further developed by later theorists such as Klein and Bowlby. While we do not engage these frameworks in detail here, they form an important background for contemporary understandings of grief and mourning as both psychological processes and socially mediated practices.

The idea of mourning as an anthropogenetic achievement gains deeper significance when viewed within a contemporary context—a time when irreversible ecological loss due to human actions increasingly defines our existence. In Leopold's writings, nature still appeared relatively stable. In his time, he and his contemporaries could not have foreseen the magnitude of the ecological crisis we face today. To them, nature was still a static entity that we could strive to return to [12]. Today, however, acknowledging the Anthropocene requires recognizing that we live in a world that is profoundly changed, or even 'after Nature' [13]. Against this backdrop, Leopold's mourning for the passenger pigeon now symbolizes a more deliberate act. In a world where irreversible loss due to human activities has become an inherent condition of our existence, acknowledging mourning as an intentional practice—one that demands emotional labour and deliberate, active participation—has taken on greater significance.

In this light, mourning in the Anthropocene emerges as both an act of recognition and resistance. Ecological grief, as articulated by Cunsolo and Ellis [6], captures the emotional pain experienced when environmental degradation disrupts familiar and valued ways of life. Similarly, the concept of solastalgia describes the paradoxical sense of homesickness that arises when one's familiar environment changes in distressing and irreversible ways [8]. Extending this further, climate-related 'pre-traumatic stress syndrome' [14] describes the anticipatory grief associated with environmental losses yet to occur, encompassing the disappearance of environmental knowledge, identities, communities and cultures. These concepts primarily address forms of grief—the inward, affective experiences of loss that take shape in response to ecological disruption. Together, they reflect how mourning has shifted from a response to past loss to a way of being in the world—a continual reckoning with living on a damaged planet [15]. In this sense, mourning names the social and cultural work of responding collectively to such grief, transforming individual sorrow into practices of shared recognition and care. This form of mourning is enduring and likely permanent, shaping not just how we live with ecological crisis, but how we live through it. It becomes a state to be navigated—an emotional and ethical practice holding the potential for transformation and collective responsibility.

Even if we do not yet fully grasp the scope of this practice, there has been a growing recognition in recent decades that environmental grief can no longer be a private burden. It must be addressed—and perhaps even carried—collectively. Cunsolo and Landman [1] view mourning as a critical part of the collective work that comes with the recognition of the Anthropocene. Within the 'labour' of mourning lies an understanding of shared vulnerability and finiteness, a commitment to collective responsibility for grief, and the recognition that 'all we have to give to the dead, to what we have lost, is our own living and our own acts of mourning and remembrance' [1, p. 8]. They see mourning as a cultural, political and ethical practice, as well as a call to responsibility to engage with what has been lost and what continues to be lost in the Anthropocene.

Likewise, Joshua Trey Barnett [12] emphasizes that mourning in the Anthropocene extends beyond mere emotional reactions—it represents an ethical and political capacity. According to Barnett, mourning ecological loss is about actively holding on to what has been lost and engaging deeply with ongoing 'earthly coexistence' [16]. Mourning in this sense serves as a practice in navigating complex human–nature relationships. Resistant mourning [17] and vigilant mourning [16] actively work to resist the trivialization of grief by rejecting premature emotional detachment or naive attempts to 'move on'. These forms of mourning insist on holding on to loss—not as passive grief, but as a sustained ethical and political engagement with what has been lost.

In the same vein, Lesley Head challenges the assumption that hope must be tied to positive emotions, arguing instead that hope is best understood as a collective practice rather than a feeling. In *Hope and Grief in the Anthropocene* [9], she explores how such practices can teach us about bearing what she calls ecological grief without becoming paralysed by it. While Head uses the term grief, her account often describes what this article has referred to as mourning: the collective and ongoing work of acknowledging loss and finding ways to respond to it together. Head's perspective insists on staying with shared loss as a basis for collective action rather than seeking personal transcendence. She suggests that hope should be decoupled from optimism and instead be rooted in action—something found 'in practices rather than in particular emotions' [9, p. 2]. In this sense, hope is not an optimistic belief that things will improve, but a commitment to pragmatic and sustained engagement with a rapidly changing world. Navigating ecological devastation requires not only mourning and bearing witness to loss but also reimagining hope as an active, collective and material practice that sustains forward movement despite uncertainty. Rather than focusing solely on grief for a lost world, Head's approach points to the need for strategies that help us live with loss while fostering the capacity to build new, more adaptive ways of being.

Summarizing the discourse on mourning in the Anthropocene highlights mourning as a political, ethical and social practice that demands sustained and vigilant engagement with ongoing ecological loss. Central to this discourse is the conviction that mourning is not merely a personal response but a collective responsibility—one requiring active recognition, resistance and care for what has been lost. Finding solace or comfort, in this sense, neither promises a resolution nor allows easy detachment; instead, it points towards means of collectively bearing what is fundamentally unbearable.

To explore this further, we turn to the practice of Birgitta Nordström, a Swedish textile artist, craft researcher and educator whose work offers a particularly interesting case of slow, materially grounded and socially attuned response to loss. We focus on her practice because it exemplifies how slow, collective and reflective processes can generate new forms of care infrastructure in response to grief. In what follows, we stay close to the textures of this practice to show how slow organizing might be cultivated as a meaningful response to mourning in the Anthropocene.

3. Following the thread: Birgitta Nordström's infant wrapping cloths

Trained in art and design with decades of experience as a weaver, Nordström has taught at the University of Gothenburg's Academy of Art and Design, where she also led research exploring the cultural and emotional dimensions of textiles in rituals

of life and death. We first met Birgitta during the launch of the Horizon Europe project *Hephaestus*. She stood before a small audience, speaking quietly about her work with infant shrouds. The careful attention she brought to each step of her craft made visible a kind of care that is both practical and profoundly ethical. We began to understand her artistic approach as a uniquely situated, materially grounded example of slow organizing in response to irrevocable loss. It is not interesting because it illustrates a general theory of craft or mourning but because it shows, in concrete terms, how time, materiality and collective care can converge to create space for shared mourning inside institutional settings like hospitals.

Data for this part of the article were gathered through a combination of ethnographic observation, interviews and conversations. We spent time with Birgitta in her workshop on Hönö, attended her presentations and joined discussions with her colleagues and collaborators. Alongside these encounters, we read her reflective writings and project materials closely. This slow, iterative process allowed for sustained dialogue and careful listening, and it made space for an understanding that could grow over time rather than be settled in advance.

Throughout this work, ethical considerations were never secondary. Birgitta herself not only participated but helped shape how her practice is represented here. This collaborative ethos aligns both with the values of slow research and with the ethics of consolation that her weaving practice embodies. Rather than speaking about grief from a distance, our intention has been to stay close to the emotional, practical and institutional complexities that shape how mourning is collectively organized.

Over the course of our collaboration, this closeness often took the form of iterative reflections and shared time: visiting Hönö, conversations over lunch and hours spent beside the loom.

On one such day, Birgitta Nordström is waiting at the small ferry connecting Hönö to the mainland. The island has about 5000 residents, but like many similar islands, this number increases drastically when people from nearby Gothenburg and tourists pour in to enjoy the summer. It is a late winter day, cold and windy, but as we reach Birgitta's home, the sun shines kindly through the kitchen windows, where we sit down to enjoy our lunch. Her house sits right on the water, overlooking the fjord. In her garden, she has built a workshop on the granite bedrock that holds her loom. She serves red beet with feta cheese and *knäckebröd* with Swedish cheese.

Nordström's craftwork engages with the worst imaginable tragedy. She weaves shrouds for stillborn. As a member of her research group put it, 'Most of us think: one day I will become a parent and I will remain a parent. No one thinks: one day I will become the parent of a dead child' [18, p. 19]. The idea of weaving infant wrapping cloths emerged when a neonatal care doctor, after hearing her lecture on funeral palls and touching the pall she had brought, expressed a spontaneous wish for a much smaller blanket to offer comfort to parents grieving the loss of a child. That wish, Birgitta explains, has carried her a long way, it is one she continuous to answer through her craft [19]. She started by experimenting with weaving techniques and materials, creating 18 handwoven blankets displayed at exhibitions and seminars. This initial work led to connections with bereaved parents, healthcare providers and clergy. Later, she focused on adapting the weaving process for industrial production, providing shrouds to hospitals for use in birth wards. To test and evaluate the relevance of the shroud, she conducted a clinical study involving five maternity wards and one gynaecological ward. As the study confirmed a clear demand, the project has continued and gained new momentum through a collaboration with *Spädbarnsfonden* (Swedish National Infant Foundation) to design a new blanket fabric for long-term production. This ensures that hospitals across Sweden can offer shrouds to grieving parents.

When Birgitta speaks about the blankets she produces, she does so with the same tenderness she brings to writing about them—gentle, but without pathos. This approach seems to keep her curiosity alive, allowing her to follow wherever the process leads. Early in our conversations, she mentions a concern that political agendas—like anti-abortionism—might co-opt her work and force it into their own causes. For Birgitta, it is crucial to let the blanket guide the process: 'I cannot write anything that does not follow the cloth into the grief', she explains.

At the beginning of the project, Birgitta felt insecure, fearing that her artistic curiosity might insensitively intrude upon the traumatic experiences of parents who had lost a child. Her solution was to open up the creative process through frequent exhibitions, inviting feedback and allowing the responses of others to guide her. As she grappled with 'the unknown' [19, p. 304]—difficult questions both about loss, memory and sorrow, as well as practical matters like size, colour and texture—she embraced a meandering yet deliberate process. This slow, open-ended approach helped her to 'activate' the blankets before they ultimately reached the hospitals, encouraging her to continue her research and alleviating her insecurities.

As we walk to her workshop, pushing aside the brambles that have grown over the paths in her garden, it strikes me that this approach is what makes Birgitta's craftwork hopeful. A shroud will never make up for the loss of a child; it brings no one back. Yet, as the slow, and sometimes tedious act of making gradually expands to embrace the needs and concerns of those drawn into it, it transforms helplessness into action—or as she puts it, 'the act of making comes to the rescue' [19, p. 313]. The first shrouds were created with the intention of weaving 'the most beautiful and tactile blankets' [19, p. 305] she could make. But the aesthetic perspective broadened as midwives guided her on the specific needs the blanket had to meet. The textile must be able to support a body that has lost its natural resilience and protect the extremely fragile skin. It also needs to absorb moisture and insulate the body, offering a sense of warmth—even though the baby must be kept cool to prevent the body from deteriorating too quickly in the open air outside the womb. When a parent holds their baby wrapped in the blanket, the woollen fabric provides a sensation of warmth, even though the child remains cold inside. For a parent cradling a lifeless child in their lap, this feeling of warmth is deeply significant. The need for the swaddling blanket is both practical and existential. There was a time when parents were actively discouraged from seeing their deceased child—urged instead to look ahead and move on. The blankets encourage and allow parents to see their child in existence, to be close, to hold it, to say goodbye. As Birgitta writes in her reflections on the process, 'The process of thinking and making unite in the act of thinking through making' [19, p. 307]. It does so, by offering the possibility of life, not by erasing pain, but by allowing one to carry on even when the circumstances

remain unchanged. In this way, paradoxically, it creates a space where hope is negotiated, nurtured and formed, even when all hope seems lost.

Birgitta interrupts the conversation to ask if it is alright for her to work while we speak. Since we sat down at her worktable in the workshop, she has been carefully tearing threads from each of the four sides of the small blankets lying in a large stack. She explains that she is making fringes to keep the edges of the shrouds as soft as possible against the skin. 'If we had been ten people here now, with five sewing machines and scissors', she tells me, 'this is the work we would do'. After the initial exploratory weaving work, she began producing the blanket fabric on an industrial scale. Later, she formed a research group to further explore the need for infant wrapping cloths for foetuses. The weaving research group consisted of friends, colleagues and students from the Academy of Art and Design in Gothenburg—some of whom had experienced the loss of a child themselves. 'I don't know what it would be like if all ten people in the room had lost a child', she explains, 'because then it sort of becomes therapeutic'. Her focus is the collective organizing around the work on the shroud, a 'collective grief that is not about my child or your child ... When you sew the blankets for a hospital that is asking for them, for an event that has not happened yet, but inevitably will. That makes a kind of grieving process possible, one that goes beyond the personal'. In this process, the roles of lecturer, colleague, health professional and student dissolved within the group, as the artistic merged tangibly with the practical needs of what needed weaving. 'It was a very special time', Nordström recalls. 'You could step away for a bit, weave some blankets, and take part in a discussion about what it meant. The fact that two of the participants had personally experienced the loss of a baby became deeply significant for all of us. They told us these blankets were needed, and that gave us a foundation to stand on' [20]. This process is inherently slow-paced, providing practitioners the necessary space and time to foster deep contemplation and attunement to the nuanced qualities of the craftwork.

As a guiding principle, which emerges organically from the process itself, this recurs across the various communities of practice that gather around the craftwork. When Birgitta talks about her engagement with Yalla Hjällbo, a work integration social enterprise in Gothenburg where women who have fled the war in Syria and Ukraine work as seamstresses, she takes great care to emphasize that their status as refugees, and what they have lost in the war, is not the primary reason they became involved in the project. What matters most is that the individual blankets are given a character of their own and infused with their own measure of care. As she puts it: 'Weaving a fabric and cutting it off the loom is a grand human narrative about life and death, but that narrative is also extremely tangible and turns into a factual situation when I am working on the loom' [19, p. 312]. Likewise, the willingness to 'follow the blanket into the grief' and the community that forms around this act is at the heart of the exhibitions Birgitta organizes. For example, at the exhibition *Songs of Sorrow*, the gallery was transformed into a small sewing factory, inviting visitors to follow the process of making the small shrouds and deciding their sizes—90 × 90 cm for a fully delivered child, 45 × 45 cm for foetuses. 'I know from previous experience that this act of choosing a size evokes deep feelings of empathy and reflection about the intended purpose of the shroud', Birgitta explains. 'We all have someone to think of—a sister who has lost a child, a brother who was meant to be, an invisible child taken from a mother in earlier times' [19, p. 313]. The proactive process of creating something that will soon be needed in a hospital brings these thoughts to the surface.

Developing genuine empathy for the users of the textiles requires careful attention to detail and sufficient time for reflection. Craft, with its slow, deliberate process, creates space for empathy to emerge through interactions with materials and contemplative practice. When asked whether this points towards a ritual use of the blanket, Nordström instinctively replies no, then pauses to reflect. To her, the craftwork serves a purpose both more universal and more immediate than inventing new mourning rituals. She illustrates this by referring to our instinctive impulse to cover a dead body: 'Care comes before ritual; it is more immediate', she explains. 'Ritual is chronology, but these shrouds have no chronology.' Instead, the blankets meet a practical need embedded within existing institutional systems. They act as a type of 'developing fluid', clarifying overlapping interests among diverse actors: the industrial textile producer Nordström collaborates with once hand-weaving alone proves insufficient; the healthcare system whose specialized language she learns to navigate before hospitals even consider participating; academic institutions and art galleries; and, crucially, craft workers, healthcare professionals and parents who have lost a child.

For all these stakeholders, producing shrouds for stillborn children brings to light needs previously sensed but not fully articulated. As a midwife expressed during a crucial meeting about hospital involvement: 'I have one reservation about this project—that it remains just a project. It has already transformed my way of working. It should be more than that. Now I see the need clearly, but what does that imply?' For Nordström, this observation marks a decisive turning point. Her aim is not to establish a new mourning ritual, but rather to support the co-creation of locally grounded, culturally sensitive practices that facilitate meaningful recalibration within institutional and social ecosystems.

Reflecting on these issues, we suggest that mourning in the Anthropocene is not only an emotional or cultural task but also an organizational one. It asks us to consider how practices, relationships and material processes are arranged to hold space for grief. This is where we turn to the idea of slow organizing—a way of describing the deliberate, careful work of creating shared, lasting forms of response to loss. We explore this further in the next section.

4. Slow organizing and the ethics of consolation

Reflecting on Birgitta Nordström's practice recalls the German philosopher Hans Blumenberg's remark: 'Circuitousness, procedural inventiveness, ritualization implies a doubt as to whether the shortest way of connecting two points is also the humane route from one to the other' [21, p. 195]. Blumenberg's suggestion is that culture is built not on efficiency, but rather on the slow cultivation of alternative paths. Rational efficiency—and the urgency dominating climate discourse—dictates that only the shortest route is legitimate, dismissing anything else as superfluous. Blumenberg critiques this rigid logic as fundamentally barbaric [21]; the shortest route may be the most direct, but it is not necessarily the most humane.

Nordström's practice vividly exemplifies this insight. Moving beyond definitions such as art project or mourning ritual, it reveals how grief can become a foundation for constructing collective ethical and emotional frameworks—structures that transform loss into practical acts of care and consolation. Within the broader discourse on grief and mourning in the Anthropocene, solace emerges here not as a suspect resolution or form of avoidance, but rather as an *organizing principle* for living with ongoing loss and suffering. Consolation shifts from being a solution to becoming an ongoing process—a collective way of bearing the unbearable. In this light, it represents a detour in the Blumenbergian sense: an indirect route that honours the need to grieve deeply, openly and communally. This 'ethics of consolation' becomes an essential organizational practice—one that paradoxically affirms life by confronting, rather than bypassing, its most profound sorrows. It becomes a form of *slow organizing*.

Historically, slowness carries negative connotations, linked to ideas of sluggishness, laziness or inefficiency. From St Augustine's moral disdain for sloth to industrial capitalism's prioritization of productivity and growth [22,23], slowness has typically been portrayed negatively—as a 'plague' [24], a barrier to innovation [25] or a sign of organizational rigidity [26]. In business and management contexts, speed and busy-ness continue to be celebrated, while slowness remains stigmatized [27].

Yet, slowness also offers a necessary counter-narrative. Emerging movements such as Slow Food [28], Cittaslow [29], slow science [30–32] and slow design [33,34] challenge conventional narratives, shifting attention from rapid efficiency to practices of sustainable engagement and mutualistic connections. Unlike deceleration, which remains tethered to the logic of acceleration by merely reducing its pace, slow organizing involves intentionally aligning human activities with processes that cannot—and ethically should not—be hurried. It is an approach to crises that deliberately organizes around processes that inherently require slowness.

Maybe this is one of the most significant lessons we can draw from Birgitta Nordström's craftwork. A central point of her practice is the patient insistence on anticipating and articulating a form of life for which those who hope for it still lack an appropriate vocabulary. In this way, her work deliberately transcends the individuality of loss. The collective practice of producing shrouds for hospitals mediates an experience of farewell before the loss has even occurred. Through careful choices of material, deliberate slowness and situated acts of care, the craftwork prepares the ground for grief, providing a form of anticipatory holding. This slow practice, learned through detail, silence and repetition, is not merely—perhaps not even primarily—the production of an object. It is a temporal practice that allows reflection to sediment into form. The loom demands not just skill but care: threads must be sorted, aligned and stretched; the weft must meet the warp, millimetre by millimetre. These actions are intimate and exacting, shaping not only the fabric but also the emotional texture of the farewell it facilitates.

As Nordström reflects, the power of her work lies in how it transforms helplessness into action—without a promise of healing, without the illusion of resolution, because there is yet no way to understand what that means. Each blanket follows a child; they are never reused. Some parents choose to keep them, folding them into memory. In this way, each shroud becomes a bearer of presence, a final act of accompaniment. Where words fail, the cloth speaks. It meets a need—a practical one, too—and absorbs grief without rushing it, without determining its duration. When the shrouds are used in hospitals, they return to the world not as artworks, but as quiet components of a care infrastructure. In their presence, they offer an alternative logic to that of efficiency or standardization. The shrouds invite hospital staff to pause, to touch, to wrap, to remember. Their softness and tactility provide a counterpoint to the sterility of clinical space. They invite holding that is more than metaphorical, even in the absence of life.

This is what makes Nordström's craftwork, at its core, an act of slow organizing. It draws people, processes, institutions and affects into alignment. It builds relationships between maker and mourner, blanket and body, individual and institution. It creates a space for collective attunement that is both pragmatic and poetic. The loom becomes a site where grief is anticipated, made visible and shared across social and temporal boundaries—where weft and warp are interlaced, one centimetre at a time. This work may not appear in statistics or policies, but it reshapes systems, nonetheless. Through the slow, careful act of weaving, helplessness is not erased but transformed. It becomes a force for gathering, for caring, for remembering. It becomes, quite literally, the thread from which hope is made.

Like all forms of organizing, this work unfolds across multiple scales. Nordström's practice does not remain confined to the loom or the studio—it radiates outward, shaping encounters, institutional practices and collective imaginaries. To fully understand how her craftwork functions as slow organizing, we can trace it across three interwoven levels: the *micro*, where emotional and material attunement takes place; the *meso*, where collaborations and routines form shared infrastructures of care; and the *macro*, where cultural imaginaries and institutional logics are gradually reshaped. In doing so, her practice expands the horizon of what we might recognize as meaningful action. It cultivates the conditions for endurance, care and a shared sense of possibility, even amid profound uncertainty.

At the *micro-level*, slow organizing begins with affective attunement: listening to what materials, people and grief have to say. By *listening* to materials, we mean attending carefully to their specific properties and responses, i.e. their texture, weight, temperature and how they interact with touch and use. This kind of attunement treats materials not as passive resources but as active participants in shaping practice, guiding the maker's decisions through their own affordances and constraints. As Birgitta Nordström demonstrates in her weaving practice, the blanket itself speaks: it guides decisions about shape, softness, weight and temperature. To follow the cloth into grief means to allow the material to structure the response, to relinquish control and accept that not all gestures of care can be rushed. Slow practices at this level are rooted in repeated, situated actions that create meaningful engagement through collective patterns, shared norms and entangled materials [35,36]. These are inherently fluid practices that do not unfold in isolation but emerge through more-than-human agency, shaped by the interplay of human emotion and non-human forces like thread, loom, textile and silence [37–39]. The craft becomes a slow conversation between hand, thread and grief. Empathy is not assumed; it is cultivated through time, care and material intimacy. In Nordström's practice, each blanket is a response to a singular loss, and each act of making is a gesture of endurance. The

refusal to reuse a shroud, the careful fringing of the blanket's edge, the tactile softness against the skin—all these decisions carry emotional weight. Here, slowness is not a lack of speed but an ethical orientation. It allows for deep reflection on the emotional dimensions of care and highlights the transformative potential of shared responsibility. These slow practices do not seek resolution or closure. Instead, they hold space for pain to be witnessed and shared, offering forms of engagement that resist quick fixes or premature consolation. Mourning, in this sense, becomes a mode of being-with—an ongoing practice shaped by attentiveness, obligation and care. By remaining open to it, slow organizing at the micro-dimension fosters the possibility of more enduring, humane forms of solidarity. It turns helplessness into grounded action.

If the micro-level shows how slow organizing begins with careful, embodied practices of attunement, this work cannot remain an individual task or process. Acts of weaving, caring and listening gain meaning as they travel between people, shaping relationships and routines. The *meso-level* considers how individual gestures are woven into collective forms of organizing—how shared practices, roles and spaces emerge to hold and structure grief. By examining these relational dynamics, we see that slow organizing is not only about the sensitivity of a single maker but about the ways communities come together, negotiate care and sustain meaningful responses over time. At the *meso-level*, slow practices expand into processes of organizing—understood as the dynamic and relational creation of socio-technical assemblages [40,41]. These assemblages, shaped by shared tools, intentions and affective attachments, enable the emergence of slow organizations: collectives that prioritize ecological, cultural and social rhythms over efficiency-driven metrics. Rather than static or hierarchical, these forms of organizing are adaptive, relational and fundamentally attuned to emergent needs. In Birgitta Nordström's weaving practice, we see how this unfolds through collective labour, through the ways people come together to work, sew, think and grieve. Her collaborations, with hospital wards, bereaved parents, refugee seamstresses, design students and art institutions, form living constellations of care that exceed the single actor or intention. These are not organizations in the conventional sense. They are not defined by formal rules or fixed roles, but by responsiveness, ethical commitment and a shared sense of purpose. For example, the involvement of Syrian and Ukrainian women in Gothenburg who sew alongside Birgitta is not framed through narratives of trauma or victimhood, but through contribution, skill and reciprocity. Similarly, when healthcare professionals engage in dialogue with artists and craftspeople, traditional disciplinary boundaries blur and new roles emerge. These workshop communities do not claim to create rituals, yet through repeated acts of stitching, weaving and adjusting, something ritualistic forms: not choreography, but shared cadence and intent. Through the imaginative and practical acts of fabulation and fabrication [42], these communities reorient prevailing epistemologies of time. Rather than reacting to grief or managing it as a temporary disruption, they build sustained practices in which mourning becomes part of an ongoing organizational rhythm. The project, initially conceived as a small weaving initiative, slowly morphs into an infrastructural recalibration. A midwife's offhand remark: *'This shouldn't remain just a project'*, signals an opening. Institutions bend slightly, tentatively, to allow space for grief. Priorities shift; policies soften. Slow organizing at this level is not just about making space for slowness, it is about making slowness: weaving it into the fabric of organizing itself. It involves iterative negotiation and collective sense-making, allowing abstract values like care and mourning to take tangible form in practices, processes and artefacts. Here, slowness becomes a participatory and proactive mode of organizing futures that are not rushed into being, but shaped through collaborative, situated labour. In this way, the meso-dimension of slow organizing offers a vital counterpoint to managerial logics of urgency. It shows that the time it takes to make a blanket, to reconfigure a ward's practice or to build trust in a workshop is not wasted time, it is the very time through which alternative, more sustainable ways of being and organizing are made possible.

At the *macro-dimension*, slow organizing becomes ecological. Not in the sense of a unified or coherent system, but as a distributed, interdependent mesh of human and non-human actors: threads, policies, institutions, exhibitions and emotions co-producing new forms of value. These are ecosystems of slowness: socio-technical and affective infrastructures that unfold gradually across domains such as healthcare, education, art and public policy [43]. They emerge through processes of attunement and entanglement, rather than design or decree.

Birgitta Nordström's weaving practice illustrates this slow ecology in motion. The work does not stay confined to the hospital or the studio; it migrates. It enters textile manufacturing systems, university syllabi, exhibitions like *Songs of Sorrow* and policy conversations around bereavement care. What began as a singular craft practice becomes infrastructural, an anticipatory device embedded in institutional life, altering how care is practiced, how grief is received and how death is prepared for. These blankets do not merely accompany grief; they anticipate it. They are created for losses that have not yet occurred but will. Unlike frameworks of degrowth or deceleration that focus primarily on resistance to economic acceleration, slowness at this level fosters systemic recalibration: a reorientation towards locally embedded, culturally specific and temporally sensitive forms of organizing. It does not offer a universal solution, but a plural, situated response that moves across sectors and scales. These slow ecosystems grow not through urgency, but through patience. They sediment slowly, through repeated interactions that may go unnoticed by metrics, but are deeply transformative over time. Importantly, this macro-dimension reveals how mourning, when approached slowly and collectively, becomes politically generative. Slowness here is not an alternative to action; it is a different modality of acting altogether. As Lesley Head [9] argues, it cultivates a hope not based in (tragic) optimism, but in the sustained capacity to live with loss and still make, still care, still organize. Hope becomes a practice, not a feeling. It is found in staying, weaving, repeating, enduring. In this sense, slow organizing can be understood as an expression of what Jonathan Lear calls *radical* hope: a hope directed towards a future goodness that remains, for now, beyond our capacity to fully imagine or articulate [44]. It is a kind of hope that persists not because we know what is coming, but precisely because we do not.

In this light, slow organizing also becomes a form of political imagination. It seeks to cultivate the material, social and institutional conditions through which mourning can be expressed, shared and sustained. What Birgitta Nordström's practice ultimately teaches us is that enduring loss in the Anthropocene requires more than technical solutions or managerial fixes—it

requires care structures that allow sorrow to breathe, and infrastructures that bend, however slightly, to accommodate what has been lost. This is what we must learn to live with in the Anthropocene. Slow organizing does not promise resolution—but it offers duration, accompaniment and the quiet work of weaving meaning from what remains. And while, in a time when so much is vanishing, this may not be nearly enough, it is nonetheless essential.

5. Concluding remarks

Reflecting on Nordström's weaving practice invites us to consider how slow organizing might be cultivated more broadly as an ethical and practical response to irreversible loss. Our research and agenda ask: how can we deliberately create spaces for shared mourning, consolation and care within the institutional, social and ecological systems that shape our lives?

There are other sites where such practices already take root, though they often remain underexplored: community hospice programmes that train volunteers in end-of-life companionship; art collectives that create memorial spaces for extinct species; urban gardening projects that reclaim derelict land as places of memory and regeneration; and indigenous-led land initiatives that refuse extractive timeframes while drawing on ancestral knowledge. Further research should investigate these different articulations of slow organizing by examining their material practices, social relations and institutional entanglements. How do they negotiate the competing demands of urgency and patience? What forms of knowledge, expertise and collaboration do they require? How do they sustain themselves across time? In exploring these questions, we can begin to map an ecology of slow practices that is diverse, context-specific and adaptive.

Developing slow organizing does not mean imposing a single model or method. Rather, it means nurturing the conditions from which alternative temporalities may emerge. In this, we invite other scholars to imagine hope not as solution, but as the patient, collective work of holding what is lost and caring for what remains. In that sense, it is less a prescription than a commitment—to keep asking what care requires of us, and to keep finding ways to do that work together.

Ethics. This study was conducted in accordance with established ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. All participants were fully informed about the aims and scope of the research and provided their voluntary consent to participate. In the case of Birgitta Nordström, who is both a practitioner and a collaborator, particular care was taken to ensure that her perspectives were accurately represented and that she retained agency over how her work and experiences were described. This collaborative approach aligns with the values of slow research and with the ethics of consolation that her weaving practice embodies. Throughout the project, we prioritized transparency, informed consent and respect for the emotional, practical and institutional dimensions of the practices we studied.

Data accessibility. This article has no additional data.

Declaration of AI use. Artificial intelligence tools were used to improve the readability and language of this work. All substantive content, interpretations and arguments remain the sole responsibility of the authors.

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